

Populism and Corruption: Do Populist Governments Gain More Approval for Anticorruption Policies?

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Abstract

This article studies the relationship between the degree of populist or pluralist rhetoric employed by governments, and how it affects the perception of anticorruption effectiveness from its citizens. By combining data from the 2021 Global Corruption Barometer survey and from the 2020 Global Party Survey, a consolidated dataset is created, including information on the degree of populist rhetoric employed, corruption approval scores, as well as socio-demographic and country-level data for each ruling government from the 47 countries. Using multilevel logistic regression analysis of the 52,925 responses from 47 countries in the dataset, the article determines that pluralist governments have higher odds of being perceived as better at handling corruption, by comparison to populist governments.

Keywords

populism; corruption; anticorruption policies; Global Corruption Barometer; Global Party Survey

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Introduction

Corruption has been around and discussed for centuries in its many forms. Given the depth and complexity of challenges corruption poses to development (Transparency International, n.d.) – including the weakening of democracy, exacerbating inequality, worsening poverty, and widening social division – it warrants a deeper study of the conditions that lead to its presence, and more importantly, the conditions which lead to its decline. The ubiquitous nature of corruption is another significant factor that makes it worth exploring in greater detail (Transparency International, n.d.) – its prevalence in multiple realms, including governments, businesses, the judiciary, civil society, etc. while also involving any and all kinds of stakeholders in its actions.

Similarly, populism has been a significant part of politics for quite some time and has often been associated with authoritarianism (Woods, 2014). An increase in populist rhetoric seems to have been employed in recent years by various political movements across the world, and often with good results (Kossow, 2019). Corruption and populism seem to symbiotically grow off each other – with corruption used to rally popular support for political agendas, and populist rhetoric used to disguise acts of corruption by the leaders once in power. Quite often, populism also appears to use corruption to dismantle democratic institutions and further propagate authoritarian policies (Mudde & Rovira Kaltwasser, 2012a).

This article was inspired by the recurring theme of various populist regimes around the world using anticorruption as part of their agenda to gain power and later undermine democracy in other ways – Jair Bolsonaro in Brazil, Viktor Orban in Hungary, Narendra Modi in India, to name a few. So, it sets out to study the after-effects of elections and examine whether populist parties in power are any better at handling corruption than pluralist parties, particularly given the anticorruption mandate that they seem to be elected on. Although there is a lot of research around democracy and corruption, given the increase in both systematic political corruption and populist rhetoric globally, this article studies both these phenomena in conjunction with each other and analyzes the interconnection between these two highly vital and well-established fields of study. The topic addressed here is the marginal comparison in anticorruption effectiveness between parties displaying populist rhetoric and parties displaying pluralist rhetoric, in order to answer to the following research question: “Do populist governments gain more approval for anticorruption policies when compared to pluralist governments?”

Using survey data from 2019 to analyze the perceptions of anticorruption approval in 47 countries globally, this article compares these perceptions to the usage of populist or pluralist rhetoric of the governments in these countries. As the data refers to a single moment in time, the variation and the justifications from the data are limited, and some elements of country-level effects on individual citizen perceptions are not entirely reflected in the analysis. This article uses logistic regression to model the factors influencing the anticorruption-effectiveness perception and analyzes a dataset compiled from the Global Corruption Barometer survey (Transparency International, 2021), and the Global Party Survey (Norris, 2020a).

We begin with a review of the existing literature on populism, pluralism, and corruption independently. Each of these phenomena is studied independently, before exploring the connections among them through the data. The literature review is followed by a section on the data, which also introduces the key variables of interest. This is followed by a section that includes descriptive explanations of the models and the results of the analysis. Finally, the article concludes with a summary of the findings, a discussion of the limitations of the study, and what can be potential next steps to explore this study further.

Theoretical background: populism, pluralism, corruption

Populism. The term 'populism' seems to have been present in literature since the last decade of the 19th century, when only 4% of the world's countries were democracies (Herre et al., 2013). However, it has seen a significantly increased occurrence in literature from the 1960s onwards and it seems to have become ever more relevant in the academic debate about democratic values ever since (Herre et al., 2013). Not surprising, perhaps, is the view taken by a lot of these authors – viewing populism as a threat to liberal democracy (Mudde, 2004). Populism seems to take on predominantly two major interpretations in the general populace – one being the politics of the people, “a highly emotional and simplistic discourse that is directed at the gut feelings of the people” (Mudde, 2004: 542). This interpretation does not serve very well the purpose of empirical academic studies. The second major interpretation is utilized to describe policies that serve to quickly please the general populace and win their support and votes, rather than being well-thought out, rationally determined best outcomes for social welfare (Mudde, 2004).

However, there is no set authority on determining the honesty of policies versus their populist appeal (Mudde, 2004). As Dahrendorf argued, “the one's populism, is the other one's democracy, and vice versa.” (Dahrendorf, 2003) The ideological ambiguity inherently present with the word can be illustrated by seeing how populists in Western Europe have conventionally been regarded as part of the so-called “radical right” due to their views on issues such as immigration (Barberà, 2021). In stark contrast, economically left-wing leaders in Central and Eastern Europe (Pirro, 2015) and Latin America (De la Torre, 2013) are also viewed as populist. As Mudde & Kaltwasser (2012) note, populism in Latin America is left-wing, economic, and inclusive, while in Europe it is right-wing, identity-based and exclusionary. It is also interesting to note that Donald Trump (Jacobs, 2023) and Bernie Sanders (Smith, 2023), two American political candidates with widely different political ideologies, have both been referred to as 'populists'.

Mudde, synthesizing the prevalent literature on populism, identifies two major points of reference – ‘the elite’ and ‘the people’ – and defines populism as “an ideology that considers society to be ultimately separated into two homogenous and antagonistic groups, ‘the pure people’ versus ‘the corrupt elite’, and which argues that politics should be an expression of the general will of the people” (Mudde, 2004: 562). A case in point is that aspects of populism could be found, often during their oppositional or ‘protest’ phase, in both the communist and fascist movements of the 20th century. Despite espousing different political ideologies, both these movements were essentially elitist, with the general masses being ruled over by a small group of powerful individuals (Mudde, 2016). While this is the most widely used definition of populism, there are other more recent schools of thought which view populism as a form of rhetoric or discourse (de Vreese et al., 2018). The rhetorical approach towards populism merely looks at the way arguments are constructed and does not make value judgements regarding the speaker's morals or truthfulness (Norris, 2020b).

It is interesting to consider the relationship between populism and democracy as they both, at their very core, refer to the sovereign rule of the people. While populism has been hailed as the purest form of democracy by some (Tännsjö, 1992), it is also considered as “potentially tyrannical and disruptive of some of the core elements of a democratic regime” (Urbinati, 2019: 114) It is interesting to note that proponents and detractors of populism have different conceptions of the idea of democracy as a whole. While the former view democracy first and foremost as the direct rule of the people, the latter take a more constitutional conception of democracy, focusing on the importance of rights, representation, and checks and balances (Abts & Rummens, 2007).

Critics of populism contend that it is a “directly undemocratic understanding of representative democracy” (Müller, 2014: 6). The general perception regarding the ability of populists to actually govern the state is not flattering. Populist parties are often viewed as protest parties which agitate against the ruling government and are unable to actually govern the state themselves (Müller, 2014). While it is true that populists have historically often struggled to hold on to power once they have obtained it (Mudde, 2016), the current social, political, and economic landscapes seem to favor populists, and display the coherence within populist conduct (Müller, 2014). Jan-Werner Müller suggests that the public arguments espoused by populists are internally coherent, albeit following a categorically different understanding of representative democracy (Müller, 2014).

Populism is usually recognized by pinpointing a clearly identifiable socioeconomic class base which supports the ideas put forth by the ‘corrupt elite’. However, empirical studies do not corroborate this approach. Those voting for populists are not necessarily less educated, nor are there typically any inclinations along gender lines. Essentially, there is no clear class or social markers which can be used to identify populist voters (Müller, 2014).

However, populism engages in a “particular moralistic imagination of politics” (Müller, 2014: 11), where a morally pure and collective group are pitted against small minorities who are not part of the authentic ‘true’ group. It is key to note that people are not considered as a single empirically whole unit, but instead, populism relies on ‘extracting the people from within the people’ (Lefort, 1988). Quite often, although not always, populists pit the hard-working people against the corrupt elite who do not really work, and, in cases of right-wing populism, also against the classes in the bottom-most ring of society; Right-wing populists render an ‘unhealthy coalition’ between the elite who do not really belong to the majority class, and the marginalized groups who do not really belong either (Müller, 2014). Examples of this include the liberal elites and racial minorities in the US, or the English-speaking elites and the lower castes such as Dalits in India, or the ‘communists’ and illegal immigrants in Italy – at least according to Silvio Berlusconi (Pullella, 2009; Rosenberg, 2011).

According to the populist modus operandi, elites are morally void due to their working only for themselves and not for the common good; and the marginalized groups are essentially undeserving minorities who do not belong to the demography – but who support the elite (Krastev, 2019). Both these groups are painted as being opposed to the authentic people, who are often symbolically identified with what Taggart notably called a ‘heartland’ (Taggart, 2000). This moral differentiation requires some concept to be used as the focal point, and populism relies on the idea of a distinct common good for this purpose. This leads to the oversimplification of policy actions that is often associated with populism. Rosanvallon goes on to argue that there is a triple simplification (Flügel-Martinsen et al., 2019.) involved in populism: first, a political-sociological simplification along the lines of the authentic common people versus the corrupt elites; second, a procedural and institutional simplification against the intermediary agents key to policy implementation; and third, a simplification of the social interlinkages and bonds which are reduced to a single indicator of homogenous identity.

Looking at factors which allow populist leaders to gradually transition into authoritarian governments, three major factors were identified to be the most relevant for the erosion of institutional checks and balances and enabling democratic backsliding: “the absence of unified governments between the executive and the legislature; the existence of a ‘power vacuum’ in the political arena; and the distribution of public support” (Ruth, 2018).

Pluralism. Pluralism as a political philosophy recognizes and affirms the diversity within a political body and appears to permit the peaceful coexistence of different interests, convictions, and lifestyles. In that sense, it is quite antithetical to the populist ideas of political philosophy. At its very

core, pluralism recognizes a multiplicity of persons and groups that, while identifiably related to one another, can also be usefully distinguished from other individuals and groups (Flathman, 2005). While political pluralism is not necessarily the same as a democracy, it is seen most commonly in democratic nations, as democracy is viewed as the most fair and effective way to moderate between discrete values (Flathman, 2005). Pluralistic ideologies appeared as an important movement in the early 1950s and now dominates the North American and by extension the Western world's view on democracy and governance (Cunningham, 1975).

One of the most famous narratives for pluralism originated from James Madison's essays, where the ex-President feared that factionalism would lead to internal conflict in the newly-formed American state; and proposes that to avoid factionalism, the many different groups – each advocating different primary principles - should be allowed to represent their ideas in order to prevent any one faction from dominating the political system (Madison et al., 1787). Building on Madison's principles, Dahl argues that many factions compete in the political sphere, and the government's role is to act as a mediator between the groups (Dahl, 2005). Interestingly, the idea of the 'common good' also plays a major role in pluralism – the hope that the conflict and dialogue between the various competing factions will result in a common good (Berlin & Lukes, 1998).

The extent to which organizational pluralism exists in a country is explained by four factors: (1) the amount of latent conflict, (2) the socioeconomic order, (3) the nature of the political regime, and (4) the concrete structure of the political institutions (Dahl, 1978).

Latent Conflict. In most countries, there seem to exist multiple different lines of cleavage, along which various factions align themselves differently, leading to conflicting pluralism in these states (La Palombara & Weiner, 2015). It is interesting to note that the various multiple conflicts are more prevalent in countries with differences in language, religion, race, or ethnic group, as opposed to countries with highly homogenous populations – where conflicts are mostly along the line of social class, and these other factors are not important enough to disturb the effects of social class.

Socioeconomic Order. A question arising in debates about organizational pluralism is whether pluralism is a product of capitalism, and if it would completely vanish in a world where the primary means of production were socially owned, rather than privately owned. Dahl argues that:

“The amount of organizational pluralism in a country does not depend on whether the economic order is capitalist, in the sense that the enterprises are privately rather than publicly or socially owned. It does depend on the extent to which decisions are decentralized, that is, on the amount of autonomy permitted to enterprises. And the amount of autonomy permitted to enterprises appears to be theoretically independent of forms of ownership, hence of capitalism and socialism as such. A capitalist order may be, but need not be, highly decentralized. A socialist order may be, but need not be, highly centralized.” (Dahl, 1978: 196)

Political Regime. Given the same extent of latent conflict in a country (i.e., there are similar differences in the population groups along the lines of language, religion, race or ethnic group), a polyarchal country will display more organization pluralism compared to a hegemonic country. This follows naturally from the fact that a hegemonic ruler would suppress all opposing dissent in the country, and thus prevent different factions to rise and gain political traction.

Concrete Political Institutions. Diversity in the number and the kind of political institutions in a country tends to have an effect on the existence of organizational pluralism. Multiparty systems increase the number and the autonomy of political parties; constitutional and political norms in some countries lead to partitioning of the governing authorities by a separation of powers and results in increasing the number of and autonomy of governmental organizations.

Corruption. Corruption has existed in many forms – and discussed in just as many contexts. Given the moral and philosophical dimensions of the phenomenon, the focus of the current academic discourse on corruption is on the policy aspect – what makes states corrupt? Can less corrupt states be built, and how can policy drive a corruption-free state (Mungiu-Pippidi & Fazekas, 2020)?

As Peter Drucker said, “What gets measured, gets managed.” This holds good particularly for the aspect of corruption in the realm of good governance. And there is little value in a measurement if it does not tell us what needs to be fixed (UNDP & Global Integrity, 2008). To successfully diagnose and solve problems of governance and institutional quality, the incidence of corruption and its evolution over time needs to be established (Mungiu-Pippidi & Fazekas, 2020). In order to establish and measure the evolution of corruption over time, it is first imperative to define it.

Historically, corruption has been defined in multiple ways. Economically, Werlin (1973) identifies corruption as the use of public office for private needs (Werlin, 1994; Blackburn et al., 2006) consider public sector corruption as the “illegal, unauthorized profiteering by officials who exploit their positions for personal gain.” (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997) emphasize governmental corruption and define it as “the sale by government officials of government property for personal gain.” (Pope & Vogl, 2000) abstracts the idea of corruption from the government and asserts that corruption can take place where opportunity and inclination are combined. What this implies is that corruption can be initiated from either side of the transaction, and that the citizens or the officials are both susceptible to offer/receive bribes in order to induce the official to give the citizen their entitlement (Melgar et al., 2010).

However, a significant hurdle to measuring corruption is how closely intertwined it is with, but simultaneously different from, the perception of corruption of the citizens. High levels of corruption perception could lead to devastating increases in corruption itself, by fostering a “culture of distrust” towards institutions and creating a tradition of gift-giving and corruption (Melgar et al., 2010). High levels of corruption perception can also have other negative effects on the state and the economy – such as the growth of institutional instability and the deterioration of relationships between citizens, institutions, and states (Melgar et al., 2010).

Differentiating between corruption and the perception of corruption is no easy task. Low salaries and poor monitoring at the public sector are not only incentives for corruption but also prompt corruption perception even when a corrupt action does not occur (Rose-Ackerman, 2003). The same happens when the bureaucracy allocates a scarce benefit to many individuals, or when the costs on the private sector by the government are high (Rose-Ackerman, 2003). Similarly, income inequality is a significant determinant of corruption: with increased inequality, the upper class can use lobbying, political influences to sway law-implementation processes and obtain favorable interpretations of the law. Income inequality can also influence corruption perception: with high inequality, “the rich are likely to believe that corruption is an acceptable way of preserving their societal position as this behavior goes unpunished and social networks of corruption expand and people will more easily justify their corrupt activities as inequality increases.” (You & Khagram, 2004: 10)

It is also found that political competition has an effect on reducing corruption. Montinola & Jackman (2002) propose that firstly, monitoring public officials is easier with freedom of information, as it limits their opportunities for corrupt behavior. Secondly, the higher turnover of power in a highly politically competitive democracy implies that politicians cannot always reliably know that particular laws will continue in practice. Therefore, these factors reduce the bribes that rent-seeking individuals pay. (Rose-Ackerman, 2003) suggests that a competitive electoral process can give politicians an incentive to reveal the untrustworthy behavior of opponents and minimize untrustworthy actions themselves. Given the effects of corruption on investment and therefore on economic growth (Mauro,

1995), it is therefore key to understand the conditions required to reduce corruption, in order to not let it hinder the economic growth and social welfare of the citizens. While it is largely accepted that institutional corruption is detrimental to national development and growth, there has historically been a school of thought which suggests that corruption might lead to an increase in economic growth (Huntington, 1968; Leff, 1964). These authors argue that corrupt practices such as bribery of government officials would allow individual citizens to avoid the bottlenecks of bureaucratic processes and delays. They also suggest that allowing government employees to charge bribes would incentivize them to work harder, thereby hastening and making the bureaucratic process more efficient.

Reviewing the literature around these three concepts, we find that there is not a significant amount of prior empirical studies undertaken which focused on the relation between corruption, populism, and how the perception of corruption-effectiveness affects the success of populist leaders and parties.

Data and methodology

In order to test the hypothesis, data from 2 different sources are merged together to study the effect of populism on corruption handling perception. The 2019 Global Party Survey – GPS (Norris, 2020a): is an international expert survey directed by Pippa Norris (Harvard University). Drawing on 1,861 party and election experts, the GPS estimates key ideological values, issue positions and populist rhetoric for 1,043 parties in 163 countries. This dataset was used to identify the rating of the political parties regarding their populist or pluralist rhetoric, which is the Independent Variable whose effect on corruption handling perception is studied. Upon filtering invalid responses for key variables, this dataset had 878 observations from 145 countries. The 2021 Global Corruption Barometer – GCB (Transparency International, 2021). Conducted by Transparency International, the GCB is the most extensive worldwide public opinion survey on views and experiences of corruption. Based on the responses of 134,967 people across 117 countries, the GCB covers questions regarding people’s views on corruption in their country in general, the change in the levels of corruption, and the effectiveness of their government in dealing with corruption, which is our dependent variable. Upon removing invalid responses for key variables, the analytical sample from this dataset was 75,603 observations.

In order to merge both the datasets together and to test the hypothesis, a third dataset was created. This dataset identifies the ruling party in 169 countries at the time of the GCB survey and includes the Press Freedom and E-Citizenship scores for these countries, from the Index of Public Integrity (Corruption Risk Forecast, n.d.). Using the Ruling Parties dataset, the GPS and the GCB data is combined in order to arrive at the Populist score for each government, taken from the ratings given to the political party. This is done by first merging the data from the GPS with the Ruling Parties dataset to match all the countries with the ruling political party and their populist score. This combined dataset is then merged with the GCB data by country, to result in the final dataset that was used for analysis. It must be noted that 23 countries had independent candidates at the helm, and therefore were not classified on the populism metric from the GPS. Upon merging the three datasets together, the final analytical sample has 52,925 observations from 47 countries.

The main variables of interest to test the hypothesis are the corruption handling effectiveness, and the position of the government on the Populist-Pluralist scale. In addition to this, the analysis also uses other socio-demographic controls: education, gender, and household income. Additionally, the perception of changes in corruption levels is also used in analysis. A summary of all the variables of interest and how it was recoded is reproduced in Table 1.

Table 1. Description and recoding of key variables.

Variable	Original scale	Recoded scale
Dependent variable (source: GCB): “How well or badly would you say the current government is handling fighting corruption in the government or haven't you heard enough to say?”	[1] “Very badly” [2] “Fairly Badly” [3] “Fairly Well” [4] “Very Well”	[1] “Corruption Handled Well.” [2] “Corruption Handled Badly”
Populism (source: GPS): Parties categorised by their ability to favour the use of populist or pluralist rhetoric	[1] Strongly Pluralist [2] Moderately Pluralist [3] Moderately Populist [4] Strongly Populist	Unchanged, stays as an ordinal variable.
Education (source: GCB): “What is your highest level of education?”	[1] No formal education ... [15] Ph.D	[1] “Primary School” [2] “High School” [3] “Tertiary education”
Gender (source: GCB): Gender of respondent	Male/Female	Male/Female
E-Citizenship (source: IPI): Degree to which citizens use digital services	Countries rated from scale of 0 - 10.	Countries rated from scale of 0 - 10.
Household income (source: GCB): “Thinking about the income your household earns, would you say that in your household ...?”	[1] "You have enough to buy what you want" [2] "You have just enough to buy what is needed" [3] "You can manage with difficulties". [4] "You need to borrow or spend savings to buy things you need" [5] "You can't buy at all what you would need"	[1] Financially worse off (1 & 2) [2] Financially Managing (3) [3] Financially Well off (4 & 5)
Corruption change perception (source: GCB): “Has the level of corruption in this country increased, decreased, or stayed the same?”	[1] ‘Increased a lot’ ... [5] ‘Decreased a lot’	[1] Corruption Increased [2] Corruption Stayed the same [3] Corruption Decreased

Table 2 provides an overview of the number of respondents by populism score belonging to each category of the variables of interest. The analytical sample consists of 15% respondents with a primary school education, 52% with a high school education, and 33% with tertiary education. The gender split between respondents is almost uniform, with 48% women and 52% men. Regarding the financial status of the respondents, 16% are in a financially bad situation, while 23% are financially borderline, and the remaining 61% are financially well to do. Of all the respondents, 37% view corruption as having stayed the same, while only 20% view corruption as having decreased, and the remaining 43% view corruption as having increased. Geographically, 22% of the respondents are from countries in South and Central America, 21% are from Asia, 52% are from Europe, and 5% are from Oceania. For each of these parameters, the first category in Table 2 is taken as the reference category and the other categories are compared to this in the regression tables.

Table 2. Summary statistics by populism score of respondent country

	Strongly populist (N=18424)	Moderately populist (N=17282)	Moderately pluralist (N=11948)	Strongly Pluralist (N=5271)	Overall (N=52625)
Education level					
Primary School	4928 (26.7%)	1875 (10.8%)	721 (6.0%)	483 (9.2%)	8007 (15.1%)
High School	9250 (50.2%)	9462 (54.8%)	6042 (50.6%)	2803 (53.2%)	27557 (52.1%)
Tertiary education	4246 (23.0%)	5945 (34.4%)	5185 (43.4%)	1985 (37.7%)	17361 (32.8%)
Gender					
Female	9089 (49.3%)	8510 (49.2%)	5392 (45.1%)	2543 (48.2%)	25534 (48.2%)
Male	9335 (50.7%)	8772 (50.8%)	6556 (54.9%)	2728 (51.8%)	27391 (51.8%)
Financial status					
Worse off	4882 (26.5%)	2572 (14.9%)	725 (6.1%)	469 (8.9%)	8648 (16.3%)
Managing	5594 (30.4%)	4591(26.6%)	1382 (11.6%)	758 (14.4%)	12325 (23.3%)
Well off	7948 (43.1%)	10119 (58.6%)	9841 (82.4%)	4044 (76.7%)	31952 (60.4%)
Perception of corruption					
Stayed the same	4993 (27.1%)	5979 (34.6%)	6067 (50.8%)	2478 (47.0%)	19517 (36.9%)
Decreased	5002 (27.1%)	3089 (17.9%)	1722 (14.4%)	817 (15.5%)	10630 (20.1%)
Increased	8429 (45.8%)	8214 (47.5%)	4159 (34.8%)	1976 (37.5%)	22778 (43.0%)
Continent					
Americas	8012 (43.5%)	1859 (10.8%)	0 (0.0%)	1833 (34.8%)	11704 (22.1%)
Asia	7521 (40.8%)	3722 (21.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	11243 (21.2%)
Europe	2514 (13.6%)	9913 (57.4%)	11510 (96.3%)	3438 (65.2%)	27375 (51.7%)
Oceania	377 (2.0%)	1788 (10.3%)	438 (3.7%)	0 (0.0%)	2603 (4.9%)

Data source: GCB 2021, GPS 2019, author's estimations.

In order to study the relationship between the variables, the paper employs binary logistic regression models with results presented as odds ratios (Pampel, 2000). Since our aim is to study the 'country effects' on socio-economic outcomes of individuals, and given that we have data at two different levels (individual and country), this requires a multilevel model. Studying country effects requires us to also account for the correlations that are induced across observations, as it would otherwise lead to standard error estimates being downwardly biased (Moulton, 1986). In multilevel models, the statistical properties of the regression estimators are well-defined if there are many large groups (Bryan & Jenkins, 2016). However, if the number of groups are small, estimates of the variance and the standard errors are imprecise and likely to be downward biased, even if the group sizes are large (Bryk & Raudenbush, 2002; Maas & Hox, 2004). Logit models require 30 countries at the very minimum to make estimations, and even then, it would only allow relatively basic estimations with any amount of accuracy (Bryan & Jenkins, 2016).

Given that the final dataset for this study has observations from 52,925 respondents (N1), and from 47 countries (N2), we can proceed with using our logit model, albeit with caution, in order to not overload the relationship with too many parameters. Specifying a higher number of parameters to attain meaningful results at the first level would inevitably overload the model at the second level, not to mention not being able to account for country-level effects which influence the individual responses,

which would then lead to omitted variable bias. Therefore, to avoid omitted variable bias arising from insufficiently controlling for country-level estimators (Allison, 2009), a modified and alternative approach to multilevel modelling is required. According to (Möhring, 2021), the fixed effects approach can be used as an alternative to the conventional multilevel models. While the multilevel approach intends to “explain country-level variation, the fixed effects approach controls for this variation” (Möhring, 2021: 5).

Results

Table 3 tabulates the column percentage of responses split between the level of populism of the government, and by the perception of the citizens regarding the governments’ ability to handle corruption. It shows that amongst countries with strongly populist parties at the helm, 54% of the citizens view them as handling corruption well, while 46% of citizens view their corruption handling ability badly. Amongst countries with moderately populist parties at the helm, only 40% of the citizens view their corruption handling ability favourably, while 60% view them as bad at handling corruption. Amongst the countries with moderately pluralist parties at the helm, 47% of the citizens view them as handling corruption well, while 53% of the citizens view them as handling corruption badly. Finally, amongst countries with strongly pluralist parties at the helm, 57% of the citizens view them as handling corruption well, while 43% look unfavourably at their governments’ ability to handle corruption.

Table 3. Perceptions of anticorruption effectiveness by level of populism of ruling party

	Strongly populist	Moderately populist	Moderately pluralist	Strongly Pluralist
Handles corruption badly	46%	60%	53%	43%
Handles corruption well	54%	40%	47%	57%

Data source: GCB 2021, GPS 2019, author’s estimations.

At the first glance, countries which have either strongly populist or strongly pluralist parties in power seem to typically fare better in the public perception when compared to countries with moderately pluralist or moderately populist parties in power. It is quite interesting to note that parties on the extreme typically fare better, and the analysis in the following section will delve into this in greater detail. The association between the perceptions of corruption handling and the type of government is statistically significant.

From Figure 1 we can observe that the higher the e-citizenship score (all countries are scored on access to digital services for their citizens, on a scale from 0 to a maximum of 10), the lower the chances of corruption being perceived as handled well in the country. Countries with the highest e-citizenship score have about 53% chances of their citizens saying corruption was handled well, while countries with the lowest e-citizenship score have about 68% chances of their citizens saying that corruption was handled well. This suggests that the higher the level of sophistication of voters in the country – for which e-citizenship was used as a proxy – the more chances that the citizens are sceptical about their governments’ ability to handle corruption well. High levels of e-citizenship are also associated with easier access to more information, which might play a role in the same direction as the one mentioned above. Figure 2 displays the predicted probabilities of the effect of two key socio-demographic controls on the dependent variable. The two controls we describe in this figure are the level of education of the respondents, and their financial status, based on their household income. It

is evident that respondents with lower levels of education, by and large, seem to have higher chances of perceiving the effectiveness of their government in handling corruption compared to respondents with higher levels of education.

Figure 1. Predicted probability of corruption handling effectiveness by e-citizenship.

Data source: GCB 2021, GPS 2019, author's estimations.

Figure 2. Predicted probability of corruption handling effectiveness by education and financial status.

Data source: GCB 2021, GPS 2019, author's estimations.

Perhaps unsurprisingly, individuals who are financially well off also seem to have higher chances of perceiving the governments' anticorruption efforts favourably compared to financially worse individuals. It is, however, interesting to note that the perceptions of those who are financially worse off do not seem to be significantly different from those whose financially status is neither very well off, nor abjectly bad.

The differences in predicted probability between the individuals with extreme financial status are, however, consistently similar across all levels of education. The difference in the predicted probability of favourable perception of their governments' corruption handling ability, between the most educated and financially worse-off individual and the least educated and financially well off individual, is about 22%.

Figure 3. Predicted probability of corruption handling effectiveness by education and gender.

Data source: GCB 2021, GPS 2019, author's estimations.

Figure 3 displays the predicted probability of the effect of the education and gender of respondents on their perception of the ability of the government to handle corruption well. While effects across education levels are similar to the ones we have discussed previously, it is interesting to note that, on the whole, women seem to have slightly higher chances of perceiving the government to have handled corruption well, when compared to men, although the differences between the perceptions of the two categories are not large enough to be statistically significant.

Finally, figure 4 displays the predicted probability of the effect of different continents on the perception of the ability of the government to handle corruption well. Individuals from Asia seem to have the highest chances of having a favourable perception of their government to handle corruption (about 73%), while individuals from Europe have lower chances (about 58%) and individuals from South and Central America have the least chances (about 48%).

Figure 4. Predicted probability of corruption handling effectiveness by continent.

Data source: GCB 2021, GPS 2019, author's estimations.

Table 4 provides logistic regression results, expressed in the form of odds ratios. Model 1 measures the effect of the degree of populism of the ruling party on the perceptions of anticorruption effectiveness of the government. Model 2 also includes sociodemographic factors, such as education level, gender, financial status, and the perception of corruption change. The dashes in the table correspond to the reference category for each variable (for example, 'Primary School Education' is the reference category for education).

The analyses presented here use odds ratios as a way of expressing the regression results instead of a typical regression coefficient. In this context, the odds ratio represents the ratio of the odds of an event occurring in one category compared to the odds of the same event occurring in another category. Generally, an odds ratio of 1.0 indicates no association between the two variables, an odds ratio greater than 1.0 indicates a positive association (i.e., as one variable increases, so does the likelihood of the other variable), and an odds ratio less than 1.0 indicates a negative association (i.e., as one variable increases, the likelihood of the other variable decreases). It's key to note that the odds ratio is a ratio of odds, not probabilities. Odds represent the likelihood of an event occurring divided by the likelihood of the event not occurring. Probabilities represent the likelihood of an event occurring divided by the total number of possible outcomes.

Model 1 shows that compared to strongly populist parties at the head of the government, moderately populist parties have 43% lower odds of being perceived as good at handling corruption by its citizens. Moderately pluralist parties, compared to strongly populist parties, have 23% lower odds of being perceived as good at handling corruption by its citizens. And finally, strongly pluralist parties in government, compared to strongly populist parties, have 16% higher odds of being perceived as good at handling corruption by its citizens. However, it is important to remember that this is a naïve estimation, without accounting for any kind of control, at neither the individual, nor the country level.

Table 4. Results from logistic regression models explaining perceptions of anticorruption effectiveness

Characteristic	Model 1		Model 2	
	Odds-ratio	95% CI	Odds-ratio	95% CI
Characteristic of ruling party				
Strongly populist	---	---	---	---
Moderately populist	0.57	0.55 – 0.60	0.63	0.60 – 0.66
Moderately pluralist	0.77	0.74 – 0.81	0.82	0.78 – 0.87
Strongly pluralist	1.16	1.09 – 1.24	1.30	1.21 – 1.39
Education level				
Primary School			---	---
High School			0.65	0.62 – 0.69
Tertiary education			0.53	0.50 – 0.57
Gender				
Female			---	---
Male			0.90	0.87 – 0.94
Financial status				
Worse off			---	---
Managing			0.90	0.85 – 0.96
Well off			1.21	1.14 – 1.28
Perception of corruption				
Stayed the same			---	---
Decreased			3.89	3.67 – 4.11
Increased			0.43	0.42 – 0.45

Data source: GCB 2021, GPS 2019, author's estimations.

Model 2 includes sociodemographic factors and controls for the responses. Socioeconomic and demographic variables can often be associated with a wide range of behaviours and attitudes, including political preferences, voting behaviour, and economic outcomes. By including these controls in a regression model, we can better understand the independent effect of the variable of interest on the outcome, while controlling for other factors that may be influencing the relationship. This can help to reduce bias and improve the accuracy and reliability of the estimated effect of the variable of interest. Additionally, including socioeconomic and demographic controls can help to identify subgroups of the population that may have unique or particularly relevant effects on the outcome.

Indeed, we see from Model 2 that including these controls has an effect on the outcomes of this model. Compared to parties categorised as strongly populist, moderately populist parties in power have 37% lower odds of being perceived as being effective in their anticorruption measures. Holding strongly populist parties as the reference, we see that moderately pluralist parties in power have 18% lower odds of being perceived as effective in their anticorruption measures. Interestingly, strongly pluralist parties in power, with the same reference, have 30% higher odds of being perceived as being effective with their anticorruption measures.

Education, as predicted, also has an influence on the outcome, with higher education corresponding to lower approval of anticorruption measures of their government. Compared to individuals with only a primary school education, we see that individuals with a high school education have 35% lower odds of viewing their government as being effective with their anticorruption measures. Individuals with tertiary education have even lower odds, 47%, of perceiving their government as being effective with their anticorruption measures. This could be explained by perhaps viewing education as a degree of sophistication of the individuals' understanding of state policies and

actions. Individuals with higher levels of education have a better, more nuanced understanding of the state action and therefore view the anticorruption measures more critically, compared to individuals with lower education, who might not critically engage with state policies and actions, and instead are swayed by the narrative from the media and the state. Gender also has an effect on the outcome variable, with male respondents having 10% lower odds than female respondents, of viewing the actions of their governments as being effective in anticorruption.

Another control we include in the model is the financial status of the respondents. Directly linked to the household income of the respondent, this control parameter would account for differences in perception patterns arising from different economic conditions of the respondent families. We see that compared to respondents who are financially worse off, respondents who are financially borderline and are managing to stay afloat with their expenses have 10% lower odds of perceiving the actions of their government as being effective in anticorruption. Financially well to do respondents, on the other hand, have 21% higher odds, compared to financially worse-off respondents, of perceiving their governments to be effective in their anticorruption policies. This is explainable by perhaps considering that financially better-placed individuals have fewer pressing economic concerns and therefore fewer reasons to be sceptical of the current actions of the government.

Actual change in corruption is also a key indicator to control for, as people's feelings towards anticorruption measures are likely influenced by how they view the presence of corruption to begin with. We see from Model 2 that compared to respondents who view corruption as having stayed the same, respondents who have perceived a decrease in corruption have higher odds of also perceiving the government to have taken effective anticorruption measures. This is in stark contrast, understandably, with respondents who have perceived an increase in corruption, with this category of individuals having 57% lower odds of perceiving the governments' anticorruption efforts favourably.

Models 3 and 4 account for country-level effects on the model, in addition to the sociodemographic controls that were already present. It is key to account for country level effects as well, as individuals from certain countries might have similar responses or perceptions towards issues and there might be intrinsic overlaps in their responses based on the country. However, as it is key to not overload the model, we only account for two viable country-effects included models. The results for these models are presented in Table 5.

We see that Model 3 already has its estimates affected slightly by including the e-citizenship score of the country, which we use as a proxy for voter sophistication, and is a country-level indicator. In Model 3, compared to parties in power which are categorised as strongly populist, moderately populist parties in power have 35% lower odds of being perceived as being effective in their anticorruption measures. Moderately pluralist parties in power, when compared to strongly pluralist parties, have 3% lower odds of being perceived as being effective in their anticorruption measures. Strongly Pluralist parties, when compared to the same reference category, have a much higher 72% higher odds of being perceived favourably regarding their anticorruption effectiveness.

We find slight changes in estimates for the education parameter as well, after accounting for e-citizenship for country-level effects, although higher education continues to correspond with lower approval of anticorruption measures of their government. Compared to individuals with only a primary school education, we see that individuals with a high school education have 33% lower odds of viewing their government as being effective with their anticorruption measures. Individuals with tertiary education have even lower odds, 43%, of perceiving their government as being effective with their anticorruption measures.

Table 5. Results from logistic regression models explaining perceptions of anticorruption effectiveness

Characteristic	Model 3		Model 4	
	Odds-ratio	95% CI	Odds-ratio	95% CI
Characteristic of ruling party				
Strongly populist	---	---	---	---
Moderately populist	0.65	0.61 – 0.68	0.56	0.52 – 0.59
Moderately pluralist	0.97	0.91 – 1.04	0.85	0.79 – 0.91
Strongly pluralist	1.72	1.58 – 1.88	1.63	1.49 – 1.77
Education level				
Primary School	---	---	---	---
High School	0.67	0.63 – 0.72	0.72	0.68 – 0.77
Tertiary education	0.57	0.54 – 0.61	0.61	0.57 – 0.65
Gender				
Female	---	---	---	---
Male	0.90	0.86 – 0.93	0.90	0.86 – 0.93
Financial status				
Worse off	---	---	---	---
Managing	0.86	0.81 – 0.92	0.92	0.86 – 0.98
Well off	1.33	1.25 – 1.42	1.35	1.27 – 1.44
Perception of corruption				
Stayed the same	---	---	---	---
Decreased	3.75	3.53 – 3.98	3.56	3.35 – 3.79
Increased	0.40	0.39 – 0.42	0.41	0.39 – 0.43
E-Citizenship (fixed effects)	0.91	0.90 – 0.93	1.00	0.98 – 1.01
Continent				
Americas			---	---
Asia			2.85	2.66 – 3.05
Europe			1.48	1.38 – 1.60

Data source: GCB 2021, GPS 2019, author's estimations.

Differences in gender continues to have similarly contrasting effects on the outcome, with men having 10% lower odds of perceiving their governments' anticorruption measures favourably. We see that compared to respondents who are financially worse off, respondents who are financially borderline and are managing to stay afloat with their expenses have 14% lower odds of perceiving the actions of their government as being effective in anticorruption. Financially well to do respondents, on the other hand, have 33% higher odds, compared to financially worse-off respondents, of perceiving their governments to be effective in their anticorruption policies. This shows an increased odds of 10% compared to the previous model, which indicates that accounting for country-fixed effects has an upward effect on the perception of anticorruption effectiveness of governments.

The effect of the perception of corruption change on anticorruption effectiveness is largely unchanged after accounting for fixed effects, as we see that compared to individuals who perceive corruption as having stayed the same over the past year, individuals who perceived a decrease in corruption have 275% higher odds of also saying that their government has been effective in its response towards corruption. Individuals who perceive an increase in corruption have 60% lower odds of viewing their governments' response to corruption favourably, when compared to individuals who perceived corruption as having stayed unchanged.

Model 4 takes the country-level specification one step further; by creating homogenous groups of countries which might have similar characteristics – here they are grouped by continent – it is possible to account for some of the patterns of responses caused by country-level factors. This is the final model that is analysed, and it has marked differences to the first model specified. In this model, keeping countries with strongly populist ruling parties as the reference, countries with moderately populist ruling parties have 44% lower odds of being perceived as being effective with their anticorruption measures. Using the same reference, countries with moderately pluralist ruling parties have 15% lower odds of being perceived as being effective with their anticorruption measures. Strongly pluralist parties at the helm, however, are associated with 63% higher odds of being viewed favourably for their anticorruption measures when compared to strongly populist parties.

Regarding the effect of education, holding individuals with a primary school education as the reference, individuals with a high school level of education have 28% lower odds of viewing their government's anticorruption efforts favourably, and individuals with tertiary education have 39% lower odds of viewing their government's anticorruption efforts favourably. The difference in odds with gender stays unchanged, with men having 10% lower odds of perceiving their governments to be effective with its anticorruption efforts, when compared to women.

We see that compared to respondents who are financially worse off, respondents who are financially borderline and are managing to stay afloat with their expenses have 8% lower odds of perceiving the actions of their government as being effective in anticorruption. Financially well to do respondents, on the other hand, have 35% higher odds, compared to financially worse-off respondents, of perceiving their governments to be effective in their anticorruption policies. It is interesting to note that compared to the previous model, the effect of e-citizenship on perception of government effectiveness regarding anticorruption seems to be statistically insignificant in Model 4.

Compared to respondents from any country in the Americas, respondents from countries in Asia have 185% higher odds of viewing their governments as being effective with their anticorruption effects. Holding the same reference, respondents from countries in Europe have 48% higher odds of perceiving their governments favourably regarding their anticorruption efforts.

Discussion, limitations, policy implications

We start this section by discussing the main limitations of our study. The GCB Survey, considered the most extensive worldwide public opinion survey on views and experiences of corruption, is a record of the perception of corruption. However, one may question the gap between the actual existence of corruption and the perception of it. Abramo (2008) suggests that personal or household experiences of bribery is not a good predictor of perceptions of corruption held by the general population. The paper also points out that the opinions in the GCB about general effects of corruption are strongly correlated with opinions about other issues – and challenges the precision of the corruption perceptions as indications of the actual prevalence of the phenomenon.

This study combines individual-level response data from the GCB survey along with country-level classification of parties from the GPS classification. Therefore, this study is undertaken at both levels – with the intention of estimating country effects on individual outcomes and perceptions. As was noted earlier (Bryan & Jenkins, 2016), relatively smaller number of countries in multi-country datasets limits the ability of regression models to provide robust conclusions about country effects. The architecture of the final dataset that the analysis is conducted on is such that there is a natural hierarchy, with observations at the individual level nested within a higher level – that of countries.

The underlying straightforward statistical requirement – of larger sample sizes being required to produce precise parameter estimates – holds good for these models as well, particularly with a large number of countries being required to obtain reliable estimates of country level effects (Bryan & Jenkins, 2016). As all the individual responses will have the same values for the country-level parameters, this will lead to country effects inducing correlations across observations. These need to be addressed in order to prevent standard error estimates from being downwardly biased (Moulton, 1986). The potential solutions to this include controlling for the issue by clustering robust standard errors but not explicitly modelling country effects (Angrist & Pischke, 2008); representing country-specific differences through country-specific intercept terms; taking the fixed-effects approach to pool together country-level data; and taking the multilevel modelling approach by pooling together the data but viewing the country effects as a random draw, instead of distinct values (Bryan & Jenkins, 2016).

This study incorporates two approaches – both clustering robust standard errors and taking the fixed effects approach. In the final analytical sample, the number of respondents ($N_1 = 52925$) is sufficiently high, but the number of countries ($N_2 = 47$), while large enough to construct basic models, is still not sufficiently large enough to perform higher-complexity estimates. It is crucial that both these sample sizes are large, as only then are the statistical properties of the parameter estimates well-defined, with consistent variability in the sampling. As the N_2 is relatively smaller in this study, the estimates of the fixed effects are unbiased (Kacker & Harville, 1981), although the estimates of the variance components and the standard errors are imprecise and likely to be downward biased (Bryk & Raudenbush, 2002). The regression outputs from this study might suffer from this problem.

Ideally, the models would include more specific controls, but that would lead to overloading the model due to the low number of countries in the dataset. This is the underlying key limitation to this dataset and analysis – the balance between describing a model which is accurate enough to estimate the effects of certain parameters, while simultaneously not overloading the model with too many parameters. As this analysis is conducted at one point in time rather than over a period of time, that leaves a lot to be explained by a singular temporal dataset. More robust modelling and precise estimations can be arrived in future studies, by including respondent survey from over a period of time spanning years, in order to accurately account for the country-fixed effects. Future analyses of this hypothesis should involve isolating the country-specific effects without overloading the model – and this would require at least two years' worth of data. The stepwise modelling approach taken in this study hopes to arrive at the best fit without overloading the model.

The implications of knowing that populist parties, despite overwhelming use of populist rhetoric to mask their corruption, still seem to have worse odds of being perceived as effective in anticorruption, are plenty. We will mention here that the dissemination of information from all ruling governments needs to be actively scrutinised, and more so with governments which employ populist rhetoric. The performance of the government in its anticorruption agenda needs to be assessed against the highest standards of transparency. Press statements and media releases from such parties need to be actively vetted and checked against objective analyses of their performance through third-party bodies such as civil society, independent government agencies, and judicial processes.

Similarly, the use of corruption issues with the intention of furthering political agendas for populist parties needs to be studied and understood better. Given that incumbent governments are often painted as corrupt by populist opposition, but only until they are elected to office, indicates a purely performative electoral campaign – one that is dropped once they are in a position to exploit the public office for private gain. Seeing as populists are often quick to make promises they are unlikely to keep (Moffitt, 2016), it is relevant to examine those promises in the first place.

The connection between populism and corruption seems inherent. The denigration of good governance and increase in mistrust of public institutions - both arising from corruption - provides the perfect platform for populists to take advantage in their electoral campaigns (Kossow, 2019). This has been evident in isolated cases across continents – Hungary, the USA, India, Brazil, etc. This thesis, however, takes a statistical analysis lens to explore the relation between populist parties and their claims on anticorruption effectiveness.

Setting out to find out if populist governments do gain more approval for their anticorruption policies than other types of parties, we find that, typically, they do not. While strongly populist governments typically fare better in the public perception of anticorruption effectiveness when compared to parties that are either moderately pluralist or moderately populist, they seem to have lower odds of garnering the same level of public approval as strongly pluralist governments. This suggests that employing high degrees of populist rhetoric in the public messaging, campaigning, and image-building is effective when compared to other parties that only moderately employ such rhetoric. However, the emphasis of pluralist governments on representing diverse interests, protecting individual rights, and promoting cooperation through the institutions of democracy and the due process of law, seems to win out over populist governments – at least when it comes to how their citizens view their performance in handling corruption.

While the field of intersection between populism and corruption is often studied through the lens of individual case studies of governments, this research studies the convergence of these fields using logistic regression to arrive at a high-level overview of perceptions of anticorruption effectiveness as a function of populist rhetoric. While the hypocrisy inherent in the duality of populism and corruption has been studied and remarked upon, this research empirically shows that populist rhetoric, while effective, is not as powerful as pluralist beliefs and faith in public institutions in shaping the perceptions of people towards how well their governments handle corruption.

Using individual-level survey data and country-level scores for key variables together, this research employs a unique tool to study this relationship. However, the more data available, the more accurate the estimations that can be made, and that holds true in this case as well. Studying the same relationship over a period of time with perception data across years would provide a better-grounded understanding of the relationship, when compared to placing the entire burden of proof on survey data from one point in time to explain differences – especially when many factors intrinsic to the country itself could influence the perception of its citizens. Future research which incorporates perceptions and country effects over the years would undoubtedly provide a deeper, richer understanding of the unique nexus between populism and corruption.

Given the threat to democratic integrity posed by the increase in populist rhetoric which is employed by more and more governments as a way to win votes and subsequently elections – coupled with the increase in corruption and an ever-widening inequality between the haves and the have-nots observed in the past decades – the importance of studying the effect of both on the common citizen becomes imperative. Particularly important, then, becomes the relationship between these phenomena, and this thesis hopes to have shed light on certain facets of this intersection between corruption and populism.

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